

IS SPACE-TIME THE INERTIA OF PRIOR ENERGY AND MASS?

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Einstein's conclusion on the energy of light, conversely forming matter, led to a profound breakthrough in the course of history, since 1905. The mathematical representation of that discovery later simplified to “ $E = MC^2$,” is here to be further investigated.

I derived my question around the investigation of his conclusion:—

“The mass of a body is a measure of its energy-content; if the energy changes by L , the mass changes in the same sense by $L/9 \times 10^{20}$, the energy being measured in ergs, and the mass in grammes.

It is not impossible that with bodies whose energy-content is variable to a high degree (e.g. with radium salts) the theory may be successfully put to the test.”

With this construct* I formed the following:—

Let Mass “ M ” be derived as unit “ ka ,” and let unit of Energy E , be “ $J=kg \cdot m^2/s^2$.” Let the speed of light “ C ” represent unit “ m/s .” The curvature of space “ R ” defined as “ $1/m$,” and its extension “space” represents unit m , and time is shown as “ t^2 .” The gravitational “ G ” constant, remains as $m^3/(kg \cdot S^2)$.

Einstein's tensor, shown as $G_{\mu\nu}$, and is defined as:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R$$

Reveals that the curvature of mass and energy, defines how space-time influences gravity. Given this, the $G_{\mu\nu}$ is defined as unit “ $1/m^2$.” The derived Stress-Energy Tensor: $T_{\mu\nu}$, describes the energy-momentum of mass and space-time, and is represented as unit “ J/m^3 .”

$$M = \frac{E}{C^2} = \frac{R \cdot S}{G \cdot t^2}$$

The space-time curvature R , which is represented as $1/m$, is written into the the notion of Mass by the Gravitational Constant.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(1/m) \cdot m}{m^3 / (kg \cdot S^2) \cdot t^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{m^3 (kg \cdot S^2)} \times \frac{1}{t^2} \\ &= \frac{kg \cdot S^2}{m^3} \times \frac{1}{t^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{kg}{m^3} X m^3$$

$$= kg$$

The correlation of kilograms of a given body of mass, and the energy constant m^3 , appear to conversely produce what we understand as a space-time curvature by $1/S^2$.

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi RS}{c^4 \cdot t^2}$$

By substituting this equation into Einsteins field equations. It is possible that the cause of a previous diminishing inertia of energy and mass, is what creates space-time; allowing for motion of matter and energy, or in a broader understanding “passing through itself (e.g. by black holes).” If the theory is held by the facts, I propose that the ‘big bang theory’ is a collision, rather than a explosion.